

EFFECT OF CHAKRA SADHANA PRACTICES ON FORCED VITAL CAPACITY AMONG ADOLESCENT BOYS

Dr. S. Jayasivarajan*, Dr. V. Duraisami, Dr. S. Kumaraguru*** & Dr. M. Elayaraja******

* Associate Professor of Physical Education, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru College of Agriculture and Research Institute, Karaikal, Puducherry

** Associate Professor & Head i/c, Department of Yoga, Tamilnadu Physical Education and Sports University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

*** Sports Officer, National Institute of Technology Goa

**** Professor, Department of Physical Education, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry

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Abstract:

The Chakras relate to physiological as well as psychic center whose structures correspond more or less with the traditional descriptions. These nerve centers are not situated inside the spinal cord itself, but lie like junctions on the interior walls of the spinal column. If you cut see that the grey matter in the cross section resembles the lotus shape and the ascending and descending tracts of nerve fibers correspond to the nadis. The purpose of the present study was to find out the effect of Chakra Sadhana Practices on forced vital capacity among Adolescent boys. The study was conducted 40 adolescent boys. Totally two groups, namely, control & experimental group I, consisting or 20 adolescent boys underwent 6 weeks practices in Chakra Sadhana Practices whereas the control group did not undergo any type of training. The forced vital capacity was measured before and after the experimentation using the standardized test to measure with spirometer. The data were analyzed by Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and it was concluded that the Chakra Sadhana Practices had significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on the forced vital capacity.

Key Words: Chakra Sadhana, Forced Vital Capacity.

Introduction:

Adolescence Boys:

The origin of the word, "adolescence" is from the latin verb. "adolescere," means, "tp grow up." Adolescence is a transitional stage of physical and mental human development that occurs between the childhood and adulthood. This transition involves biological, social and psychological changes. The teenage years are from ages 13 to 19. In fact, early adolescence is the most difficult phase of life, as children cannot express their problems correctly because their power of expression and their knowledge of their own psychology are not mature enough. Due to physical changes, hormonal changes, and constantly changing moods,. Teenaged children have many unexplained and unexpressed problems.

Balancing the Hormones:

Sexual consciousness should develop when the child is able to balance his reaction in his mind. Nowadays, as children grow up, their pineal gland begins to decay and their pituitary gland begins to develop automatically, before the child possesses the mental and emotional stability to cope with such hormonal drives. As a result, the whole confusion starts at the wrong time. The child becomes restless because he/she is not physically ready to express this new affecting their behavior. If we can delay emotional growth, in relation to physical growth, the child's stability is enhanced greatly. To remove these kinds of problems of children, we will have to study the emotional effect of the hormones in the system. Sometimes, such problems are also caused by an imbalance of the thyroid hormones.

The Chakars:

The literal meaning of the word Chakra is 'Wheel' or 'Circle' but in the yogic context a better translation of the Sanskrit word is 'Vortex' or ' Whirlpool'. The Chakras are vortices of Psychic energy and they are visualized and experienced as circular movement of energy at particular rates of vibration. In each person there are myriads of chakras, but in the practices of tantra and yoga, only a few Principal ones are utilized. These chakras Span the full spectrum of man's being, from the gross to the subtle.

The Chakras relate to physiological as well as psychic center whose structures correspond more or less with the traditional descriptions. These nerve centers are not situated inside the spinal cord itself, but lie like junctions on the interior walls of the spinal column. If you cut see that the grey matter in the cross section resembles the lotus shape and the ascending and descending tracts of nerve fibers correspond to the nadis. These communicating nerve fibers control the different physiological function of that portion of the body. Many books state that the chakras are reservoirs of power but this is not true. A Chakras is like a centrally placed electricity pole from electrical wires are run to different places, house and street lights in the vicinity, this arrangement is the same for each one chakras. The nadis emerge from each chakra carry Prana in both directions. There is a

forward and backward Pranic motion in the nadis, the outgoing communication and the incoming reaction enter and level the chakras in the form of this pranic flow in the corresponding nadis.

Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of Chakra Sadhana Practices on forced vital capacity among Adolescent boys.

Methods and Materials:

The sample for the present study consists of 40 Adolescent boys from Karaikal. The subjects were selected using random sampling method. Their age ranged from 14-17 years. They were divided into two groups namely Experimental group and control group (n=40), and used Wet Spiro meter was administrated to them. Experimental group was under the practice of chakra sadhana practices for the period of 6 weeks both morning at 7.30 to 8.15 for the period of 6 weeks. The training programme was administered for forty five minutes per session. The control group did not engage in any special activities. The load was fixed based on the pilot study. The pre test and post test were taken before and after the experimental training programme. The test was conducted Wet Spiro meter for forced vital capacity on each end of the cessations and data was recorded. Analysis of covariance was used as a test of significance.

Training Schedule:

Experimental Group: Chakra Sadhana

Attention is to be brought to them when performing Chakra Sadhana Practices.

S.No	Chakra Sadhana Practices Corse	Duration
1	Practice for Ajna	First to Third week
2	Practice for Mooladhara	
3	Practice for Swatdhisthana	
4	Practice for Manipura	
5	Practice for anahata	Fourth to Sixth week
6	Practice for Vishuddhi	
7	Practice for binduVisarga	
8	Practice for integrated chakra awareness	

Group II: Control Group (No Practice)

The statistical analysis comparing initial and final means of forced vital capacity due to Chakra Sadhana Practices Among adolescent boys is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Forced Vital Capacity of Experimental and Control Group

Test	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Df	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F
Pre-Test Mean	2.35	2.29	Between	1	0	0	0.05
			Within	38	5.8	0.15	
Post-Test Mean	3.06	2.17	Between	1	7.86	7.86	181.73*
			Within	38	1.64	0.04	
Adjusted Mean	3.06	2.18	Between	1	7.86	7.86	250.51*
			Within	37	1.16	0.03	

*significant.

Table value for df 1 and 38 was 3.21 Table value for df 1 and 37 was 3.22.

The obtained adjusted mean values were presented through bar diagram in figure 1.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram on Ordered Pre and Post Means of Forced Vital Capacity

Discussions on the Findings of Forced Vital Capacity:

Taking into consideration of the pretest means and posttest means adjusted posttest means were determined and analysis of covariance was done and the obtained F value 250.51 was greater than the required value of 3.22. And hence it was accepted that the Chakra Sadhana training significantly improved the forced vital capacity of the adolescent boys.

Conclusion of the Research:

The analysis of co-variance of forced vital capacity indicated that experimental group I (Chakra Sadhana), and group II (Control group), were significantly improved the forced vital capacity. It may be due to the effect of Chakra Sadhana Training.

Nearly everything in life requires balance. Chakra Sadhana Training on its own is a good step toward a healthy life style. However, as individual, it is important to malaise that we need to work on our body as well as our mind. We can use Chakra Sadhana Training not only as part of a program to improve forced vital capacity, but also as a way to assist in attaining other goals. Chakra sadhana practices improved the efficiency of forced vital capacity significantly.

On the basis of the findings of the study, it may be considered that the chakra sadhana practices program is very useful method of training for the forced vital capacity to improve forced vital capacity within shorter duration. But it only retains for twenty to thirty days in chakra sadhana practices the improvement was slow but it could retain the efficiency for longer duration.

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